

The Quantum Koszul-Plücker Picture

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Emmerson recently provided me with two papers on Koszul-Plücker theory. Importantly, he interprets *zero-fold coverings* as a degenerate case of a covering space, corresponding to an initial object in the category of ∞ -topoi. The key idea is that a zero-fold covering behaves as a "degenerate" or collapsed structure, which locally resembles finite coverings but collapses globally. This concept can be expressed in algebraic terms through a projective morphism.

The equation representing a zero-fold covering is:

$$\text{Spec}(Z/0) = \aleph_y \in \infty,$$

where $\aleph_y$ denotes an uncountable cardinal (linked to infinite coverings), and $\text{Spec}(Z/0)$ refers to the spectrum of the zero element, corresponding to the collapse of the covering structure.

In quantum systems, degeneracy (e.g., energy levels with the same eigenvalue) often corresponds to multiple quantum states collapsing to the same value, which is conceptually similar to the idea of zero-fold coverings collapsing to a trivial structure. To formalize this relationship, we can introduce a novel equation that links the *degeneracy of a quantum state* to the zero-fold covering structure.

1 Generacy and Degeneracy

Let's define the *generacy* $\mathcal{G}$ of a quantum state (the inverse of the number of degenerate states associated with a particular energy level) and relate it to the zero-fold covering in terms of its collapse. We can introduce the following equation:

$$\mathcal{G} = \lim_{n \rightarrow 0} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\Phi_i}{\text{Spec}(Z/n)},$$

where:

- $\mathcal{G}$ represents the generacy (or degeneracy) of the quantum state.
- Φ_i represents the quantum state wavefunctions (eigenfunctions) corresponding to the energy level E .
- $\text{Spec}(Z/n)$ represents the spectrum of an n -fold covering, and in the limit $n \rightarrow 0$, it approaches the zero-fold covering $\text{Spec}(Z/0)$.

1.1 Interpretation

As the number of covering spaces n tends toward zero (i.e., we approach the degenerate case), the generacy $\mathcal{G}$ corresponds to the number of degenerate states collapsing into the same energy level. The zero-fold covering describes the total collapse of the system's structure, which parallels the situation where all quantum states collapse to a single energy level, exhibiting degeneracy.

2 Entanglement

The algebraic structure of entanglement can be captured through the interplay of Plücker coordinates and Koszul complexes, which describe the relations among subspaces of a Hilbert space in quantum mechanics. In the case of a bipartite quantum system, the Hilbert space can be factored as $\mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B$, where $\mathcal{H}_A$ and $\mathcal{H}_B$ represent the state spaces of subsystems A and B , respectively. The entangled states in this system correspond to subspaces of the total Hilbert space that cannot be decomposed as a simple product of states in A and B . Plücker coordinates are natural tools to describe these subspaces geometrically, as they provide a projective embedding of the Grassmannian $\text{Gr}(k, n)$, the space of k -dimensional subspaces of an n -dimensional vector space. These coordinates satisfy the Plücker relations, quadratic equations that constrain the coordinates to lie on the Grassmannian, analogous to how entangled states satisfy constraints imposed by the structure of their subsystems.

For a bipartite system, consider a pure state $|\psi\rangle \in \mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B$ with a Schmidt decomposition of the form:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^r \lambda_i |a_i\rangle \otimes |b_i\rangle,$$

where $\{|a_i\rangle\}$ and $\{|b_i\rangle\}$ are orthonormal bases for $\mathcal{H}_A$ and $\mathcal{H}_B$, respectively, and λ_i are the Schmidt coefficients. The number of non-zero Schmidt coefficients r gives the rank of entanglement. The space spanned by $\{|a_i\rangle \otimes |b_i\rangle\}$ is a subspace of the total Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B$, and this subspace can be described by Plücker coordinates. The Plücker embedding maps this subspace into projective space $\mathbb{P}(\wedge^r(\mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B))$, where the Plücker coordinates $p_{i_1 \dots i_r}$ satisfy the quadratic Plücker relations that define the Grassmannian.

In the context of Koszul complexes, we can further explore the structure of entanglement by interpreting the exterior algebra $\wedge^\bullet(\mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B)$ as a Koszul complex. A Koszul complex is defined by a sequence of elements $\{f_i\}$ in a ring R , and its homology reveals the structure of the space in terms of exactness or failure of exactness at various levels. In the quantum case, the elements $\{f_i\}$ correspond to the basis states $\{|a_i\rangle \otimes |b_i\rangle\}$, and the differentials in the Koszul complex describe the entanglement structure by identifying the relationships between these states. The homology of this complex can provide insight into the degree of entanglement, with vanishing homology at higher degrees indicating maximal entanglement.

The Koszul-Plücker-Emmerson theory extends this understanding by linking the algebraic structure of Koszul complexes and Plücker embeddings with conformal structures in topological spaces. Specifically, Emmerson's work introduces a way to connect Plücker coordinates with the conformal pullbacks of entangled subspaces, represented by Koszul complexes. Given a Koszul complex $K(f_1, f_2, \dots, f_r)$ over a commutative ring R , where f_i are associated with the states $|a_i\rangle \otimes |b_i\rangle$, the corresponding Plücker coordinates describe how the entanglement evolves as the system changes. The second homotopy group π_2 of the associated topological space, evaluated at these states, reveals the conformal structure of the entangled system, providing an algebraic measure of the pullback to

lower-dimensional subspaces. This can be expressed as:

$$\pi_2(M, f_i) \cong \{p_{i_1 \dots i_r}\},$$

where the Plücker coordinates $p_{i_1 \dots i_r}$ capture the conformal transformation properties of the system under entanglement.

Finally, the Plücker-Koszul homology of the entangled system can be understood through the stabilization of cohomology in infinite Koszul complexes. In the case of highly entangled systems, the infinite sequence of basis states $\{|a_i\rangle \otimes |b_i\rangle\}$ leads to an infinite Koszul complex, where the cohomology stabilizes as the sequence becomes effectively regular. This stabilization reflects the persistence of certain entanglement structures even as the system size increases. The Plücker relations, in this context, ensure that the subspaces describing entangled states remain well-defined in higher-dimensional Hilbert spaces, leading to a stable algebraic structure. The cohomology stabilization can be expressed as:

$$H^k(K) = 0 \quad \text{for } k > r,$$

where r is the rank of the entanglement, corresponding to the number of non-zero Schmidt coefficients.

The following commutative diagram explains the relationship:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 H_A \otimes H_B & \longrightarrow & \bigoplus_{i=1}^r \lambda_i |a_i\rangle \otimes |b_i\rangle \\
 \text{Koszul complex} \downarrow & & \downarrow \text{Plücker coordinates} \\
 \bigwedge^\bullet (H_A \otimes H_B) & \longrightarrow & P(\bigwedge^r (H_A \otimes H_B)) \\
 \text{Cohomology stabilization} \downarrow & & \downarrow \text{Entanglement structure} \\
 H^\bullet(K) = 0 & \longrightarrow & \text{Stable Entangled Subspace}
 \end{array}$$

where H_A and H_B are Hilbert spaces.

A References

- [1] P. Emmerson, *Koszul-Plücker Relations and their Applications*, (2024)
- [2] P. Emmerson, *Integration of Buchanan's Method with Koszul-Plücker Theory*, (2024)
- [3] Y.B. Jia, *Plücker Coordinates for Lines in the Space*, (2024)